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Implementation of the Sports Activities in Promoting Student Engagement: A Case Study

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Abstract

This study paper aims to investigate the successful implementation of the sports activities in a selected school in the First District of Bohol in promoting student engagement. A case study design was utilized, employing qualitative study methods and purposive sampling in selecting the respondents. Five (5) physical education teachers who met the criteria participated in this study. The result of this study highlights the successful implementation of sports activities in a selected school in the First District of Bohol, wherein they implemented different sports activities that could maximize student engagement and contribute to high performing athletes. They also actively participated in different sports events and were able to bag different awards and always have a spot in higher competitions. This successful implementation and active participation of the school in different sports events was made achievable by the collaborative effort of the different stakeholders. This study benefits students, educators, school administrators, and future researchers by giving valuable insights into implementing sports activities that could promote student engagement.

Keywords: *successful implementation, sports activities, student engagement*

Introduction

Sports are one of the activities offered in the Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) curriculum, particularly in the Physical Education component in the Junior High School (Curriculum Guide, 2016). In addition, sports activities related to schools are offered in Junior High Schools (JHS) at different year levels; these include individual and dual sports, team sports, sports officiating, and active recreation for sports.

The promotion of student engagement is an important factor in effective teaching practice. According to Wylie (2021), one way to increase student engagement is by encouraging social learning, like engaging them in sports activities. Additionally, it is stated that student engagement becomes higher when they collaborate with their peers. Sports activities bring them closer, whether competing or collaborating, and these interactions contribute to their social and personal growth (Yang, 2022).

The selected school in the First District of Bohol is one of the biggest schools in the Division of Bohol in terms of student population and does not have enough space or playing area that allow students to engage in sports activities. They also implement two shifting schedule schemes, but despite these, the selected school has performed well in different sports fields; they actively participate, bag different awards, and always have a spot during provincial and regional competitions from 2017 to 2023 and even sent athletes to Palarong Pambansa in the year 2023.

Sports activity implementation plays an important role in student engagement. However, there is a need for an in-depth study to understand the factors that contribute to the successful implementation of sports activities. To that end, this descriptive case study examines the implementation of sports activities in the selected school and explores the reasons behind its excellent performance in different sports. This study aims to investigate the implementation of the sports activities in promoting student engagement.

Research Questions

This study aims to describe the implementation of the sports activities in the Junior High School in a selected school in the First District of Bohol in promoting student engagement in the school year 2017-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the sports activities offered in Junior High School?
2. What are the facilities and equipment used in the different sports activities?
3. What are the challenges of the teachers associated with the implementation of sports activities?
4. What are the strategies or techniques used in coping with the challenges associated with the implementation of sports activities?
5. What are the factors that contribute to the school's success despite the challenges?

Literature Review

Student engagement is integral to students' success (Fung et al., 2018). The Glossary of Education Reform defines student engagement as the level of curiosity, attention, optimism, passion, and enthusiasm that a student shows when being taught or simply learning, extending their motivation to learn and succeed. In the study conducted by Devito (2016), it was stated that an engaged student is involved in learning and doing extracurricular activities. Engaging in sports improves overall well-being owing to the positive impact

on mental and social development, particularly during the preparatory phase (Clark et al., 2015).

One way to promote student engagement is through sports activities. Sports activities allow socialization and the development of leadership skills, discipline, and teamwork. Sports programs promote collaboration, sportsmanship, regard for others, and fair play. Ghildiyal (2015) claims that sports facilitate character development beyond physical advantages by fostering leadership skills, analytical and strategic thinking, risk-taking, and goal-setting. Additionally, according to Zayas (2018), participation in sports activities can have positive results for students, and it makes students feel that they are more part of the environment and helps them increase their feeling of belongingness in the community. Moreover, students' engagement in sports benefits them positively and builds character development, which enriches opportunities for them (Timothy, 2023). The relationship that can be formed in sports participation is crucial to student belonging and engagement.

One of the challenges in implementing sports activities to promote student engagement is the inadequate facilities and equipment. Physical education activities must have adequate facilities and equipment to succeed. According to Awuma (2015), facilities and equipment are crucial to the growth of sports. This study highlights how crucial it is for every school to have enough standardized training facilities and equipment for physical education activities. Good sports programs operate at their peak efficiency only when backed by appropriate equipment in good condition. Every school indeed needs facilities and equipment to provide high-quality instruction.

Another challenge for physical educators in implementing sports activities is the large class size. Large class size is one of the challenges in implementing sports activities. This can have a negative impact on student engagement, student learning, and opportunities for students to have challenging, fulfilling, and successful experiences with physical activities like sports (Ghatti, 2018). In a classroom with a large number of students, it is a challenge for the teacher to keep all students engaged in learning (Saikat, 2022). Additionally, Large class sizes can have some consequences, which serve as a challenge for physical educators. These include student disengagement, increased risk of a student injury, and the need for a teacher to address more behavioral issues (Hatfield, 2018). Moreover, according to (Wang et al., 2022), large class sizes can negatively impact the student's level of satisfaction and teacher interaction. This could result in the unsuccessful implementation of sports activities and promoting student engagement.

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to investigate the implementation of sports activities in promoting student engagement in a selected school in the First District of Bohol. This study utilized a descriptive case study approach to meet this objective. This study design gives the researcher an in-depth understanding of the implementation of sports activities in promoting student engagement. This study used a qualitative study methodology utilizing interviews to gather enough information from the participants. The purpose of choosing a qualitative method is to understand the implementation of sports activities to promote student engagement at the selected school.

Participants

The participants of this study were the Junior High School Physical Education Teachers in a selected school in the First District of Bohol. Five (5) junior high school physical education teachers met the criteria for participation in this study. Purposive sampling was employed to select the respondents. The selection of participants in this study considers that the PE teacher must have a degree related to teaching MAPEH or PE. Moreover, the teacher must be teaching MAPEH or PE in the Junior High School and must have at least three (3) years of teaching experience. Furthermore, the PE teacher must voluntarily agree to participate in the study. On the other hand, a PE teacher who is a graduate of any degree not related to teaching MAPEH and PE but teaches PE classes cannot participate in this study. Moreover, a teacher who teaches Senior High School and has less than three (3) years of experience in teaching PE classes cannot participate, and if the teacher is forced to participate in the study.

Instrument

In this study, the researchers used an interview that consisted of open-ended questions. The interview was designed to gather information from participants about their experiences in implementing sports activities to promote student engagement. The researchers chose this instrument because it allows the participants to express themselves without the limitations of predetermined answer choices. This leads to more detailed responses, revealing insights and avoiding biases in the question-phrasing mode. The interview questions were validated with the help of the adviser and the panel members.

Procedure

The researchers asked permission from the principal of the selected school in the First District of Bohol. The researchers asked permission from the qualified respondents to participate in this study, wherein they met the inclusions stated by the study participants. Before the interview was conducted, guidelines and instructions were clearly explained to the respondents.

The PE teachers were invited to participate in the study through a transparent and clear communication channel. Moreover, this invitation concisely summarizes the study's purpose and objectives. Participants were given in-depth information in an informed

consent form outlining the procedures, potential risks and benefits, privacy safeguards, and the voluntary nature of participation. In addition, participants were strongly encouraged to pose inquiries and seek clarification to ensure they fully understood the study. Participants were given enough time to consider their choices, free from any compulsion or pressure, allowing them to make an informed decision regarding whether or not to participate in the study. This process emphasized respect for individual autonomy and ascertained that participants participated in the study voluntarily and clearly understood their roles and rights.

Data Analysis

After the interview, the researchers transcribed the data. After transcribing the data, the researchers asked an English major to check and verify that the transcribed data corresponded or matched the answers to the respondents. Thematic analysis was used to interpret and analyze the data.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the study process, ethical considerations were considered. The respondents' confidentiality and anonymity were protected by obtaining informed consent. In addition, researchers did not use any information such as the name, gender, age, and life status of the respondents in gathering the data to ensure the respondents' anonymity and privacy. This also ensures voluntary participation among the participants. Hence, the participants might withdraw from participating in the study at any time without any consequences if they feel violated. Rest assured that the data gathered from this study was used for educational purposes only. Furthermore, only the researchers can access the recorded interview, which was deleted after the data was transcribed, to ensure the confidentiality and privacy of the respondents' responses.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Sports Activities Offered in Junior High School*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Specific Sports Activities</i>
Structured Pathway of Sporting Events	Intramural Meet District Meet Sub-Congressional Meet Congressional Meet Provincial Meet CVIRAA Palarong Pambansa
Curriculum-Aligned Sports Activities	Arnis Softball Basketball Volleyball Badminton Inter-section sports competitions

The selected school in the First District of Bohol offers different sports activities to promote student engagement including structured pathways of sporting events and the curriculum-aligned sports activities. The structured pathway of sporting events in Junior High School (JHS) is a planned sequence of sporting activities commencing from local or district competitions to higher competitions, while the curriculum-aligned activities align with the Department of Education's MAPEH curriculum. Student-athletes from the selected school go through these various structured pathways and different sports activities that help them train and improve their skills in their chosen sport, contributing a lot to their development, which can help them excel in sports.

Table 2. *Facilities and Equipment Utilized in the Different Sports Activities*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Specific Facilities And Equipment</i>
Varied Equipment for Diverse Sports	Table Tennis Equipment Lawn Tennis Equipment Badminton Equipment Gymnastics Equipment Dancesports Costume Arnis Stick Volleyball Equipment Basketball Equipment Softball Equipment
Community-Based Facilities	Lawn Tennis Court Basketball Court Volleyball Court Sepak Takraw Court

 Plaza
 Cultural Center

The selected school in the First District of Bohol received a Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) given by the Department of Education (DepEd) and a School Educational Fund (SEF) from the Local Government Unit (LGU), which will be used to spend on activities and necessities that support learning programs, including implementing sports activities. The school purchases sports equipment annually for those sports that they participate in various meets, including individual, dual, and team sports, to ensure that students can have a better experience in sports engagement. In addition, there is personal ownership of equipment among the students who are into sports. The school has limited space for playing areas, and the school's covered court was destroyed by typhoon Odette. With this, the school needs to seek external support in order to hold sports activities outside the school premises.

Table 3. *Challenges Encountered in Implementing Sports Activities*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Specific Challenges</i>
Time Constraints	Limited Practical Engagement Limited time
Availability and Quality of Equipment	Cannot focus on specific areas due to time constraints Equipment will not last long Equipment was no longer in good condition Inadequate Equipment
Accessibility of the Venue and Safety Concerns	Plaza is distant from the school Unavailability of the playing area within the school Access outside the school
Lack of Expertise and Training	Absence of formal training and lack of proficiency Do not feel confident in teaching its related skills

The selected school in the First District of Bohol encountered challenges in implementing sports activities. One of those is the time constraints caused by the two-shifting schedule due to its high population of students. Another challenge is the quality and availability of sports equipment, wherein they consider the budget when purchasing equipment, which results in low-quality equipment that cannot last longer. The inadequacy of sports facilities within the school serves as another challenge because they have to utilize the facilities and venues outside the school, raising concerns about the safety of the students. Furthermore, some of the teachers lack expertise and formal training in a specific sport, which could lead to potential safety issues and an increased risk of injuries to the students.

Table 4. *Strategies or Techniques Used in Coping Up with the Challenges Associated with the Implementation of Sports Activities*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Specific Strategies Or Techniques</i>
Resourcefulness	Modification of Equipment Utilization of open space
Multimedia Integration	Utilization of vacant rooms Making use of multimedia Integration of video instruction Utilization of televisions
Hands-On Instruction and Practical Emphasis	Direct teaching Actual demonstrations Heavily emphasize performance task

The selected school in the First District of Bohol has a successful implementation of sports activities amidst the challenges. Resourcefulness, such as making use of the open spaces and vacant classrooms for practices, adapting facilities, and modifying the equipment, have become their strategies. They also established a strong partnership with the Local Government Unit (LGU) to use their plaza, cultural center, and oval. Additionally, the use of multimedia has been utilized by the teachers to address the problem of unfamiliarity of the sport providing proper ideas and execution for the students. Hands-on and practical emphasis is also utilized by the teachers for them to give proper execution as they demonstrate a certain sport and integrate video demonstrations to develop the skills of the student despite the limited time and limited practical engagement. Therefore, challenges in implementing sports activities are not a hindrance for students to engage in sports activities as long as teachers have the strategies and techniques to cope with the challenges.

The selected school in the First District of Bohol has several factors that contribute to the school's success despite the challenges they encountered in implementing the sports activities, such as students' factors, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, strategic athlete selection, teachers' dedication, and stakeholders and school support. Strategic selection of athletes is one of those factors wherein they can choose the best athletes for that particular sport. Moreover, the remarkable characteristics and attitudes of the student-athletes, combined with their commitment and dedication to sports, contribute a lot to their excellent performance in sports. Additionally, they are competitive, knowing that they are motivated both intrinsically and extrinsically. Lastly, they have the support of the different stakeholders in terms

of financial and moral support from the very beginning, which helps them excel amidst the different challenges. With this support, the school excelled in sports with the help of the collective efforts of the school and the community.

Table 5. *Factors that Contribute to Successful Sports Implementation*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Specific Experiences</i>
Student Factor	Student's character and attitude Student's talents and skills Students are disciplined Students are determined Students are competitive
Intrinsic Motivation	Athletes are performing well because they are motivated Students are committed Students have passion in sports Students have willingness to participate
Extrinsic Motivation	Awards and recognition Cash incentives from the LGU Medals and certificates given by the school Grades will not be affected
Strategic Athletes Selection	Profiling of the students Selected athlete who excelled during tryouts
Teachers' Dedication	Strong command of the subject matter Constant follow-up Hire a trainer Monetary contribution
Stakeholders Support	School Education Fund from the LGU Cash assistance from the LGU LGU provides transportation Support from the parents
School Support	Athletes are supported by the school

Conclusions

The selected school in the First District of Bohol has demonstrated a proactive involvement in various sports events organized by the Department of Education (DepEd), which enable students to hone and advance their athletic abilities. The school also implements competency-based sports activities, as stated in the curriculum. Such activity provides a structured framework that focuses on assessing and enhancing individual competencies, ensuring a targeted approach to learning. This also enables students to identify and work on their strengths and weaknesses, leading to more effective skill improvement. The school's involvement in different sports events maximizes student engagement and skill development, contributing to high-performing athletes. The successful implementation of the sports activities at the selected school in the First District of Bohol is also attributed to students' commitment to participation and motivation to excel.

The active participation of the school in different sports events has been made achievable through the collaborative support of the school, the parents, the Local Government Unit, and other stakeholders. This collective effort has facilitated students' engagement and provided valuable opportunities to participate, compete, and enhance their skills. Thus, creating an environment where sports thrive.

The researchers proposed several recommendations, including continuous provision of sports activities, fair athlete selection, continued provision of awards and recognition, teacher training, and constant communication with stakeholders. Additionally, future researchers are encouraged to create a study about the student-athletes experiences and focus on factors that contribute to their engagement and success in sports. In conclusion, these recommendations are beneficial for enhancing the school's implementation of sports activities that promote student engagement.

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